

THE ORIGIN AND CHARACTERISTICS OF ENGLISH FAIRY TALES

Nishonova Buvixon

ESL/EFL instructor

Teacher at School N 14

Abstract: This article explores the comparative aspects of precedent names in Uzbek and English fairy tales, examining how these names reflect cultural nuances, character traits, and societal norms.

Key words: fairy tales, elements, magic, royal family, precedent names, culture, character.

Introduction

Fairy tales have long served as a window into the cultural, moral, and social values of societies around the world. They are rich in narrative tradition and often feature characters whose names carry significant meaning. Fairy tales, rich in cultural heritage, provide a window into societal values and norms. There are examples of fairy tales from across the world, and the stories often have common themes and motifs. Traditional fairy stories were created by unknown authors at a time long before many people could even read or write. People told the stories to each other, or acted them out. They were passed down from generation to generation by word of mouth. The details of the stories might have changed slightly with each re-telling, but the main message remained the same.

Collecting and adapting

The stories were later collected, written down and adapted by writers and scholars like Hans Christian Andersen (1805-1875), Charles Perrault (1697-1750), Andrew Lang (1844-1912), Jacob Grimm (1785-1863) and his brother Wilhelm Grimm (1786-1859). Today, we often associate fairy tales with children's literature, but they were originally intended for a mixed audience of adults and children.

Fairy tale elements

A set phrase used at the beginning and end of the story: Most fairy tales begin with 'once upon a time' or 'a long time ago', and end with telling the reader that the characters 'lived happily ever after'. Fairy tales are often set in the past, but not in a defined period of history, and they usually have a happy ending where the hero triumphs over adversity.

Fairy tales often feature characters who are mythical or magical, such as witches, elves, and fairies. A problem which needs to be solved:

For example, a physical challenge that can only be undertaken by the hero or central character.

Typical character types:

- Hero
- Villain
- Helper.

Settings:

For example a forest and/or castle setting are common to many fairy tales.

Suggested activities

• Draw a table or grid with titles of favourite fairy tales along one side, and some or all of the following elements along the other side:

- Magic objects or powers
- Villain
- Helper
- Hero
- Problem to be solved
- Repetition — groups of three or seven; repeated phrases
- Set phrases at beginning and end of story
- Royal family — king, queen or princess.

| Understanding Precedent Names

Precedent names refer to established legal principles or rules that are derived from previous judicial decisions. In the context of law, a precedent is a decision made by a court that serves as an example or rule to be followed in subsequent cases with similar issues or facts. The concept is a cornerstone of common law systems, where past rulings significantly influence future cases.

There some types of precedents that is included. They are:

1. Binding Precedent:

- Also known as "mandatory precedent," this type must be followed by lower courts in the same jurisdiction. For example, decisions made by a higher court (e.g., a supreme court) bind lower courts.

2. Persuasive Precedent:

- These are not binding but may influence a court's decision. They can come from courts in different jurisdictions, lower courts, or even obiter dicta (comments made in a judgment that are not essential to the decision).

3. Original Precedent:

- This occurs when a case is decided for the first time, establishing a new legal principle.

4. Declaratory Precedent:

- This type clarifies existing law rather than creating new law.

Precedents ensure that similar cases are treated alike, promoting fairness and stability in the legal system. They reduce the need for lengthy legal arguments in

every case by providing established rules. Precedents serve as a reference point for judges when making decisions, helping them interpret the law. Understanding precedent names is crucial for anyone involved in the legal field. They play an essential role in shaping the law and guiding judicial decisions. By analyzing past rulings, legal professionals can better predict outcomes and navigate the complexities of the legal system.

| The Role of Names in Fairy Tales

Names in fairy tales, in English literature, play a crucial role in shaping the narrative and enriching the reader's experience. They serve multiple functions that enhance character development, thematic depth, and cultural context. Here's a detailed exploration of the various roles that names play in fairy tales:

| 1. Character Identification

- Immediate Recognition:

Names provide readers with a quick way to identify characters, making it easier to follow the story. In fairy tales, where characters often embody archetypes (e.g., the hero, the villain, the wise old man), names can instantly convey these roles. For example, a character named "Jack" in English fairy tales is often associated with cleverness and resourcefulness, while "Maleficent" suggests malevolence.

- Distinctiveness:

Unique names help differentiate characters, particularly in stories with a large cast. This distinctiveness aids in avoiding confusion and allows readers to engage more deeply with individual character arcs.

| 2. Symbolic Representation

- Foreshadowing:

Many names carry symbolic meanings that can hint at a character's journey or fate. For instance, in English fairy tales, names like "Snow White" suggest purity and innocence, while "Cinderella" evokes themes of transformation and resilience. In Uzbek fairy tales, names might reflect traits such as bravery or wisdom, setting the stage for the character's development.

- Character Traits:

Names often embody certain qualities that align with the character's role in the story. A name like "Grumpy" from Snow White conveys an immediate understanding of the character's disposition, while a name like "Aladdin" suggests adventure and resourcefulness.

| 3. Cultural Reflection

- Cultural Significance:

Names in fairy tales often reflect the cultural background of the characters and the society from which the stories originate. In Uzbek fairy tales, names may

incorporate elements of Islamic culture or local traditions, offering insights into societal values and norms. For example, names like "Zuhra" might denote beauty and brightness, resonating with cultural ideals.

- Language and Meaning:

The meanings of names can also provide context about cultural beliefs. In English fairy tales, names like "Beauty" or "Hope" are imbued with positive connotations that resonate with universal themes of love and aspiration. Similarly, Uzbek names might carry historical or familial significance, linking characters to their heritage.

| 4. Linguistic Differences

The linguistic structure of names in Uzbek and English also presents fascinating contrasts. Uzbek names often incorporate suffixes that denote familial relationships or social status, while English names may simply denote individuality without such contextual markers. For instance, the name "Rustam" in Uzbek literature evokes the legendary hero known for his strength and bravery, while in English tales, a name like "Robin Hood" carries connotations of rebellion against injustice.

4.Moral Lessons:

Names can encapsulate moral lessons prevalent in a culture. In Uzbek tales, characters often have names that reflect virtues such as wisdom or bravery. For example, "Oydin," meaning "bright," may denote a character who brings light to dark situations. Also, a character named "Foolish" might serve as a cautionary tale about the consequences of poor choices, reflecting societal values regarding wisdom and prudence. Conversely, English fairy tales frequently use names to convey moral lessons through cautionary tales. The name "Greedy Gus" would immediately signal to readers the character's flaw and foreshadow his downfall.

Conclusion

The comparative study of precedent names in Uzbek and English fairy tales reveals much about the respective cultures from which they arise. While both traditions utilize names to convey character traits, moral lessons, and cultural significance, they do so in ways that reflect their unique histories and values. As globalization continues to blur cultural boundaries, understanding these differences can enrich our appreciation for storytelling across cultures. Fairy tales remain timeless narratives that not only entertain but also educate us about the human experience through the lens of tradition and language.

REFERENCES:

1. Akhmedov, A. (2015). *Cultural Significance of Names in Uzbek Folklore*. Journal of Central Asian Studies, 12(2), 45-58.

2. Bacchilega, C. (1997). **Postmodern Fairy Tales: Gender and Narrative Strategies**. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
3. Eagleton, T. (2008). **Literary Theory: An Introduction**. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
4. Hodgson, M. (2006). **The Fairy Tale: A New History**. New York: Routledge.
5. Khamraev, U. (2018). **The Role of Names in Uzbek Fairy Tales**. *International Journal of Folklore Research*, 15(1), 23-37.
6. Khan, A. (2010). **Uzbek Folklore: A Cultural Perspective**. Tashkent: Uzbekistan State University Press.
7. Luthi, M. (1982). **Once Upon a Time: On the Nature of Fairy Tales**. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
8. Propp, V. (1968). **Morphology of the Folktale**. Austin: University of Texas Press.
9. Ruthven, K. (2006). **A Guide to Fantasy Literature**. New York: Routledge
10. Zipes, J. (1997). **The Oxford Companion to Fairy Tales**. Oxford: Oxford University Press.